

**THE GEOPOLITICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE NEAR EAST REGION
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Annotation: This article is focused on the geopolitics of the Near East region. It analyzes the geopolitical importance of the Near East region in international relations. Furthermore, a brief discussion is held on the political and geopolitical relations, opinions, and the interaction of external forces on inter-state opinions among the countries in the region. The impact of external forces on the region's politics post-Cold War is examined, including the process of stabilization of opinions between Iran and Saudi Arabia. Moreover, the article elucidates the stabilization process of opinions between China and the Islamic Republic of Iran with Saudi Arabia neighboring China.

Keywords: Near East region, USA, Saudi Arabia, Persian Gulf, USA, Russia, Syria, China.

Europe and Africa, located at the confluence of the Mediterranean and Indian oceans, the Middle East region is one of the most important regions in the world. The Middle East region includes countries such as Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Qatar, Oman, the United Arab Emirates, Iran, Iraq, Bahrain, as well as Cyprus, Syria, Israel, Lebanon, Palestine, Turkey, Yemen, and Egypt. The average income of the populations of these countries is lower compared to the oil-exporting countries of the Persian Gulf. However, Turkey and Israel have relatively high

incomes among non-oil countries. The reason for this is Israel's technological and commercial advantage, while Turkey benefits from its abundant water resources and highly developed and traditional infrastructure. Saudi Arabia, Iran, Turkey are the most powerful and assertive countries in the region striving for leadership and dominance..¹

The Middle East region has become a central hub for international trade, cultural exchange, and political influence throughout human history due to its convenient geographical location. It holds great importance from both geopolitical and economic perspectives. In recent times, its economic significance has been on the rise.

Firstly, the Middle East possesses the world's largest oil and gas reserves. According to estimates, approximately 30% of global oil and 20% of natural gas are produced in the Middle East region. Countries like Saudi Arabia and Kuwait derive a significant portion of their internal revenue from oil and gas reserves.

The abundance of natural resources, particularly oil and gas, has not only shaped the economic landscape of the region but has also influenced global markets and geopolitical dynamics. The Middle East's strategic position as a major supplier of these vital resources has given it a considerable economic and political clout on the world stage..²

¹ Khalid Rahman. International Factors Affecting the Middle East: Trends and Implications // Policy Perspectives. – Volume 1. – 2008. P.22 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/42909183>

² Importance of the Middle East to the World History // <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-middle-east-world-history-emem-udoh>

Additionally, Saudi Arabia alone holds 17% of the world's oil reserves (Table 1).

Furthermore, the region's trading importance has also increased. For instance, the Suez Canal is one of the most crucial shipping routes globally, used to transport oil and other goods from Africa, Asia, and Europe. Moreover, in this region, renowned airports like Dubai International Airport and Kuwait International Airport serve as key transit hubs for global passenger and cargo transportation. The Middle East is a significant trading hub, with cities like Dubai and Qatar experiencing growth in international investments and the development of new manufacturing industries. Several countries in the Middle East have become integral parts of the global financial centers.³

As emphasized above, the Middle East region is considered a key area due to its oil, gas, and natural resources, making it a strategically and economically important region that attracts the interest of other countries and intensifies competition in the region. In the past, during the onset of World War I, the Middle East was under the rule of Great Britain and France, while the Cold War between the United States and the Soviet Union escalated military build-up and maneuvers in the region. With the withdrawal of British and French forces and the

³Importance of the Middle East to the World History // <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-middle-east-world-history-emem-udoh>

fragmentation of the Soviet Union, the United States emerged as the dominant foreign power in the region.

The historical events and power shifts in the Middle East have had profound implications on its geopolitical landscape, shaping alliances, conflicts, and resource exploitation in the region. The strategic significance of the Middle East continues to influence global politics and economics, making it a focal point for international relations and competition among major powers.

Countries outside the Middle East often compete for economic, political, and other strategic benefits from the region, frequently intertwining external affairs with internal matters in the region. These interactions often further strengthen internal divisions. This can be exemplified by the case of Syria. In 2011, the Syrian population expressed discontent with the presidency of Bashar al-Assad. The government's response to suppress this discontent led to the beginning of a civil war. During this period, countries like the United States, Russia, Iran, and European nations pursued their interests. Specifically, Iran and Russia provided long-term support to the Bashar al-Assad government. Bashar al-Assad's continued presidency allowed them to influence internal affairs and maintain leverage over the state. In contrast, the United States and European countries supported opposing factions to remove Assad from power. Additionally, Israel conducted air strikes. Alongside these actions, the local dissent in Syria evolved into an international proxy war.

The involvement of external actors in the internal affairs of countries like Syria often exacerbates conflicts and prolongs instability. These complexities highlight how regional dynamics are entangled with global interests and power struggles, shaping the landscape of international relations in the Middle East.

In the Middle East, territorial disputes among countries have persisted for many years. The presence of border disputes, unresolved Kurdish issues between Iran and Turkey, and the Arab-Israeli conflict have created high levels of tension in

the region. It is known that the stability and prosperity of the region are also linked to external factors, with external powers always playing a significant role. At the same time, existing tensions in the region are being exploited artificially through the involvement of external forces.

Currently, the Middle East can be described as follows: on one hand, Sunni Arab states maintaining good relations with Israel and the USA; on the other hand, Turkey, Qatar, and Muslim Brotherhood allies, as well as Iran and its allies like Hezbollah, Shia conflicts in Iraq, and the Syrian government. Competition among them unfolds in Libya, Syria, Iraq, and Yemen.

The intricate web of alliances, rivalries, and conflicts in the Middle East demonstrates the complex nature of the region's geopolitics, where internal and external factors converge to shape its dynamics. The involvement of various regional and global actors further complicates the situation, making the Middle East a focal point for international relations and strategic maneuvering

After the end of the Cold War between the United States and the Soviet Union, China actively assumed a dominant position and significantly contributed to the international system governed by Western powers. The global financial crisis in 2008 and the refugee crisis in Europe in 2010 weakened the dominant position of the USA and other major Western powers in the international system. China gradually took on the role of a "key player" in building the international system, increasing its global influence accordingly.

Located at the crossroads of East Asia, Europe, and Africa, the Middle East features crucial sea trade routes like the Suez Canal, Bab el-Mandeb, and the Strait of Hormuz. Serving as a vital crossroads linking the East and the West, it facilitates the simplification of relations between the Atlantic and Indian Oceans, holding great strategic importance in global politics, economy, and military affairs.

Moreover, the Silk Road in the arid Middle East and the main corridor of the 21st-century maritime Silk Road play a significant role in advancing the "One Belt,

One Road" initiative both on land and at sea, promoting connectivity and development in both arid and maritime regions.

Since the 1990s, China has been gradually strengthening its economic and trade relations with Middle Eastern countries. The establishment of the Belt and Road Initiative in 2013 further deepened cooperation between China and the Middle East, expanding beyond traditional sectors like energy resources and infrastructure to embrace emerging areas like digital economy and green energy. By 2022, China had become the main trading partner for Middle Eastern countries, with half of its oil imports coming from the region. The collaboration and sometimes rivalry between China and Middle Eastern countries not only impact bilateral economic and trade development and the advancement of the Belt and Road Initiative but also influence China's energy security and national interests. The evolving dynamics between China and the Middle East illustrate the intricate interconnectedness between global powers and regional actors, shaping the landscape of international relations and economic development..⁴.

Saudi Arabia and Iran are both major powers in the Middle East, each exerting significant influence in the region, often highlighting the Sunni and Shia spheres of Islam that have had noticeable impacts in the region. Following the "Arab Spring," Arab states faced significant pressure and challenges, pushing for better development and a greater focus on progress, which created exceptional needs for Saudi Arabia. The establishment of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) presented new opportunities for Saudi Arabia. Since President Xi Jinping's visit to Saudi Arabia in 2016, China and Saudi Arabia have solidified their strategic partnership, expanding cooperation in various fields, developing a comprehensive and mutually beneficial partnership over time. By 2022, China positioned itself as a significant partner with both Iran and Saudi Arabia through a "comprehensive partnership" in the Middle East. Both Saudi Arabia and Iran are energy giants. Iran

⁴ O'sha yerda

controls the vital energy transit point, the Strait of Hormuz. Due to vast energy reserves, strategic geographical locations, and religious significance, both countries hold crucial positions in the Middle East and even on a global scale, making them attractive to a state aiming to become the dominant player under China's "One Belt, One Road" initiative. However, due to historical reasons, serious disputes and rivalries have existed between Iran and Saudi Arabia for many decades, with strained diplomatic relations. China acts as one of the world's most important stabilizing forces by not interfering in the internal affairs of other countries and maintaining a neutral stance in economic, trade, and diplomatic exchanges with both Iran and Saudi Arabia, safeguarding an impartial position. In March 2023, China intervened to encourage dialogue between Iran and Saudi Arabia through mediation efforts, working together for international peace and security. This reconciliation between the two major states presents a new model for resolving various conflicts in the Middle East and offers the opportunity for reconciliation for countries like Yemen and Syria, while providing a strong boost for the sustainable development of the Belt and Road Initiative. The primary goal perceived from the convergence between Iran and China is to reduce U.S. influence in the region.

The intricate relationships and power dynamics in the Middle East showcase the complexities of geopolitics, where historical tensions, economic interests, and diplomatic maneuvers intertwine to shape the region's future trajectory.⁵

Based on the aforementioned circumstances, the following conclusions can be drawn regarding the geopolitical significance of the Middle East in international relations:

1. Despite accounting for only 4% of global GDP, the Middle East holds significant importance in the world economy when considering its two primary

⁵ Dr.Masoud Behzadifar. Evolution of China's Interaction with Middle Eastern Countries under the Belt and Road Initiative // PLOS ONE,2023. // <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10635491/#pone.0293426.ref001>

natural resources: oil and gas. These resources power automobiles, provide cities with electricity, and serve as the primary energy source for global shipping. Controlling a significant portion of the world's energy supply, fluctuations in oil and gas prices in the Middle East affect prices globally. A significant portion of the world's oil supply, about 20% of total world oil trade, passes through the strategically vital Strait of Hormuz, which is a chokepoint separating the Persian Gulf and the Gulf of Oman. Due to its strategic importance, experts consider the Strait of Hormuz as the lifeline of the world economy.

2. Secondly, the region's advantageous location as a trading and transit hub positions the Middle East at the crossroads of Europe, Asia, and Africa, historically serving as a center of civilizations. Currently, the Middle East serves as a pivotal trade center and a hub for cultural exchange. With ancient art, beliefs, and languages gathered from almost all borders, the Middle East has become a lively hub on the world stage.

3. Thirdly, the Middle East is the birthplace and center of three major monotheistic faiths: Judaism, Christianity, and Islam. These religions play a vital role in international relations. The holy sites for each religion in the Middle East, particularly the revered cities of Mecca and Medina for Muslims, continue to have global significance today, influencing global processes.

In summary, the Middle East's unique geopolitical, economic, and religious characteristics place it at the center of global affairs, shaping international relations, energy markets, and cultural exchanges worldwide. The region's significance goes beyond its borders, impacting global dynamics and interactions in various spheres of life.

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